

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE SEEDS OF *CITRULLUS COLOCYNTHIS*, SCHRADER. PART II*

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The seeds are intensely bitter and contain an alkaloid, a polysachharide or a glucoside, an enzyme or enzymes reducing β -glucosides and tannin. The seeds contain 21% of a pale brownish yellow oil, phytosterolin (Ipuranol), two phytosterols, two hydrocarbons and also saponin material and a sugar. From the active bitter principle a very small amount of an yellow crystalline compound melting at 176° has been isolated.

Power and Moore (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 99) examined the pulp of the fruit (Turkish variety) separately from the seeds and the following substances were isolated: citrullol, a dihydric alcohol; an amorphous alkaloidal substance possessing an extremely bitter taste and representing one of the purgative principles of the fruit. α -elaterin, a small amount of hentriacontane, a phytosterol and a mixture of fatty acids. They found the seeds comprising 75.5% of the peeled fruit to contain traces of an alkaloidal principle, a small amount of an enzyme hydrolysing β -glucosides, and fatty oil.

The present investigation deals with the examination of the seeds only and the following compounds have been isolated: a phytosterolin (Ipuranol), two phytosterols, one melting at $122-24^{\circ}$ and the other at $98-100^{\circ}$; two hydrocarbons, one melting at $59-60^{\circ}$ and the other at $54-56^{\circ}$; also saponin material and a sugar. The seeds are found to be intensely bitter and contain an alkaloid, polysachharide or a glucoside, an enzyme or enzymes reducing β -glucosides, and tannin. From the active bitter principle a very small amount of an yellow crystalline compound (m. p. 176°) has been isolated. The fatty oil has been completely investigated separately (cf. Part I, this issue, p: 515).

It will be observed from the literature (cf. Part I) that there has been no thorough chemical examination of the Colocynth seeds. Most of the earlier investigators confined their work to the investigations of the pulp of the fruit. In view of the medicinal value of Colocynth in modern pharmacy and the absence of any work on the Indian Colocynth, the present investigation was undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preliminary Examination

Test for Alkaloids.—The crushed seeds (15 g.) were digested with Prollius' solution for about 2 hours and the mixture filtered. The filtrate gave tests for the presence of alkaloids.

The crushed seeds (15 g.) were shaken for 5 minutes with 150 c.c. of a mixture of chloroform and ethyl ether. Concentrated ammonia (5 c.c.) and water were then added and the mixture shaken for about 2 hours and 15 c.c. of water were added and filtered. The filtrate was extracted with 1% sulphuric acid solution. The acid extract was made ammoniacal and extracted with the same solvent mixture as above and finally extracted with 1% sulphuric acid solution. This acid extract showed the presence of alkaloids when tested with the usual alkaloid reagents.

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Test for Enzymes.—The crushed seeds (100 g.) after extraction with petroleum ether were dried and shaken with water for about 12 hours. The supernatant liquid was then expressed and filtered with difficulty. A quantity of redistilled rectified spirit was added to the filtrate, when a thick, light colored precipitate was produced which was filtered and washed with a little alcohol and dried in a desiccator.

This substance was found to contain an appreciable amount of reducing substances and some inorganic material. It reduced β -glucoside indicating the presence of an enzyme.

Steam distillation.—The crushed seeds (200 g.) were distilled with steam and about 700 c.c. of the distillate were collected. The distillate, which was not acidic, was then extracted with ether. The extract was dried and the solvent removed. A very small amount of a pale yellow oily mass was thus obtained which could not be identified.

Test for Starch, other Carbohydrates, Tannins, etc.—The crushed seeds (15 g.) were digested with water on a hot water-bath for about half an hour and the supernatant liquid was decanted and filtered. The filtrate gave tests for the presence of tannins and a reducing material. A portion of the filtrate, on hydrolysis, showed the presence of a good amount of a polysachharide or a glucoside. This latter reduction may be due to the glucose formed by the hydrolysis of the glucoside supposed to be present in the seeds. The bitter taste of the original filtrate indicates that a glucoside is at least partially responsible for the heavy reduction after hydrolysis.

The crushed seeds (4 kg.) were extracted with redistilled rectified spirit in a modified soxhlet apparatus (cf. Tummin Katti, this *Journal*, 1930, 7, 210). The extract was completely freed from the solvent when a dark brown, viscous material, bitter in taste, was left over. This material was spread on fine filter-paper pulp, dried and extracted in a soxhlet (*loc. cit.*) successively with petroleum ether (b.p. 30°-60°), ethyl ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate and ethyl alcohol, and the various extracts were examined completely.

Petroleum Ether Extract

This is a brown viscous material and has a faint bitter taste. In order to isolate this bitter principle, the extract was shaken with 90% alcohol and the alcohol was removed and filtered.

(A) *Alcohol-soluble portion.*—The solvent was removed and the residue, dissolved in chloroform, was poured into a large volume of petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°). There was no precipitate, not even a turbidity on keeping the mixture overnight. Evidently the bitter principle did not come down in the petroleum ether extract.

The mixture of solvents was then distilled off and the residue saponified. The soap was dried on fine, dry, filter-paper pulp and extracted with ether in a soxhlet. Thus the above material was separated into (i) sodium salts of the fatty acids from the saponifiable material and (ii) ether-soluble unsaponifiable matter. The former material was not examined further since the fatty oil has been completely investigated. The latter material was washed free of soap and the solvent removed. A white solid material separated on concentrating the extract, which was removed by filtration; the filtrate on standing deposited some more of the solid material.

Isolation of Phytosterolin (Ipuranol, m.p. 287°-90°).—The white solid material recovered from above was refluxed with charcoal and crystallised from 95% alcohol.

The white shining crystals gave all the colour reactions of phytosterols, m.p. 287-90°. The acetate melted at 162-64°. This compound is Ipuranol in conformity with the substance isolated by Tummin Katti (*loc. cit.*) from the seeds of *Caesalpinia bonducella* and by Power and co-workers from a number of plant materials.

Isolation of a Phytosterol (m.p. 122-24°).—The filtrate from above after removal of the solid material (Ipuranol) was freed from the solvent and the pale yellow viscous residue was digested with charcoal and crystallised from 75% alcohol, as white glistening solid, m.p. 122-124°, which gave all the colour tests of phytosterols. It gave an acetate, m.p. 109-10°.

(B) *Alcohol-insoluble portion*—The dark viscous oil was saponified and the resulting soap was spread on filter-paper pulp, dried and extracted with ether. During the course of extraction, a white solid powder separated out.

Unsaponifiable Matter. Isolation of a Phytosterol (m.p. 98-100°).—The ether-insoluble white powder from above was refluxed with charcoal and crystallised from 95% alcohol. The snow-white crystals melted at 98-100° and gave all the colour tests of phytosterols.

Isolation of a Hydrocarbon (m.p. 59-60°).—The clear, light yellow, ether-soluble portion from above was washed free of soap and the solvent distilled. The viscous residue was crystallised from 80% alcohol when beautiful snow-white glistening plates melting at 59-60° were obtained. The insolubility of this solid material in concentrated sulphuric acid even after warming on the water-bath suggested that it might be a saturated hydrocarbon, but the quantity was too small for further analysis.

Ethyl Ether Extract

The syrupy, viscous, dark red extract, freed from the last traces of ether, was found to be intensely bitter. The extract was dissolved in chloroform and poured into a large excess of petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°). A pale yellow powder immediately separated out. This powder was carefully filtered and washed with petroleum ether. After some time, the powder set to a dark brown, resinous mass. This material is intensely bitter.

The bitter principle softens at 108° and completely melts at 112°. It is readily soluble in chloroform, alcohol, glacial acetic acid and benzene; slightly soluble in water and sparingly soluble in petroleum ether.

Elementary analysis of the bitter principle proved the presence of nitrogen and absence of sulphur and halogens.

The bitter principle gave tests for the presence of an alkaloid and a reducing material. A portion of the bitter principle, on hydrolysis, gave tests for the presence of a considerable amount of a polysaccharide. This may be due to the glucose formed by the hydrolysis of the glucoside supposed to be present in the bitter principle.

These tests indicate the presence of an alkaloid, a reducing material and a polysaccharide or a glucoside in the bitter principle.

Isolation of an yellow crystalline compound.—A portion of the bitter material was dissolved in alcohol and treated with an alcoholic solution of lead acetate. The precipitate was filtered and the filtrate freed from excess of lead by passing a current of hydrogen sulphide. The filtrate from this was evaporated to a syrup and refluxed

with acetic ether for several hours. On cooling, a small amount of an yellow crystalline material separated out. This was filtered and the filtrate on concentration yielded a little more of this solid. This compound melted at 176° . Further examination of this crystalline material could not be undertaken for want of sufficient material.

The mixture of solvents (chloroform and petroleum ether) after removing all the bitter principle was distilled, when a very small amount of a pale yellow viscous oil was obtained.

Chloroform Extract

The dark brown, syrupy extract was found to be slightly bitter. Attempts to separate any bitter principle from this extract were, however, unsuccessful. On crystallisations from 80% alcohol a fraction of a white solid was obtained, m.p. $54-56^{\circ}$. Its insolubility in concentrated sulphuric acid even after warming on a water-bath, suggested that it might be a saturated hydrocarbon, but the quantity was too small to permit further investigation. No other compound could be separated from this extract.

Ethyl Acetate Extract

The brown extract was found to be slightly bitter. This was refluxed with charcoal and crystallised from 95% alcohol when a white powdery substance separated out. This material was too small for further work. No other compound could be isolated from this extract.

Alcohol Extract

The dark brown extract after complete removal of the solvent was dissolved in water. It was bitter in taste. The aqueous solution was treated with basic lead acetate and the pale yellow precipitate was filtered and washed with water.

Identification of Saponin.—The precipitate from above was suspended in water and decomposed by passing a current of hydrogen sulphide and filtered. The filtrate on concentration under reduced pressure gave a very small amount of a dark red semi-solid and an yellow liquid which frothed considerably on shaking. The semi-solid material was found to be bitter. No definite crystalline compound could be isolated from this semi-solid material. The yellow solution on hydrolysis reduced Fehling's solution after heating for a long time and keeping for several hours. These properties indicate the presence of a saponin material in the liquid.

Identification of Sugar.—The filtrate and the washings from above, after removing the precipitates of lead salts, were mixed together, delead, filtered, and the filtrate concentrated to a small bulk, when a very small amount of white shining needles separated, which were removed by filtration. The filtrate was then digested with alcohol (redistilled rectified spirit) for over 2 hours and cooled. No compound separated from this. A portion of this filtrate on hydrolysis gave a faint indication of the presence of a reducing material.

The needle-shaped crystals from above had a very faint sweet taste and their melting point was above 300° .

The syrupy liquid after removal of the needle-shaped crystals, gave an osazone, m.p. $204-205^{\circ}$. No other compound could be isolated from the alcohol extract.